

Reflections on Nigeria, Africa and Blacks in the Diaspora: An Agenda for Symbiotic Relationship in the Emerging Global Dynamics.

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Abstract

This paper explores the nexus between Pan-Africanism and transcontinental solidarity of Africa and the peoples of African descent scattered all over the globe that has become a living historical epoch referred to as the African Diaspora. Whether it be force majeure or voluntary migrations, many of the dispersed peoples have regrouped to constitute themselves and are making waves in their new countries. This is because the Diaspora question has become a very vibrant force in contemporary international relations. The paper however, digested the mutual relations and responsibilities that should exist between Africans at home and those abroad, that have not been able to adequately address the persistent problems of Black liberation, an ancestral home, equality and more recently, in tackling the dilemma of democracy, good governance and development generally. It is, therefore, the argument that a good number of the Diasporas are domiciled in the developed countries and have acquired skills that could be channeled to benefit Nigeria and Africa; if Nigeria recognizes the talents and take appropriate measures to tap them for her developmental challenges. This is because Nigeria can and should make use of the Africans in the diaspora through a well-coordinated effort to strike a mutually beneficial deal for both Nigeria and Africa; that is yet to be fructified as is the case of the Jewish Diaspora. The paper utilized both primary and secondary sources to quarry the African Diaspora question that have catalyzed human history.

Key words: *Nigeria, Africa, Diaspora, Blacks, Pan-Africanism, and Negritude.*

Introduction

Africa is the cradle of man and home of the blacks. But blacks are not found in Africa alone; indeed they are found in all the regions of the world. Their presence all over the globe is a product of some historical forces. Today, these Africans outside the continent are known as Africans in the Diaspora. The Diaspora concept is used to refer to the body of Jews or the Jewish community outside Palestine or modern Israel since the dispersion of the Jews outside of Israel from the sixth century BC when they were exiled to Babylon until the present time. It is also used to describe the community of people, with a common cultural identity that were dispersed from their aboriginal homeland. This dispersion could be in several forms such as persecution, slave trade, or a force majeure arising from economic or political pressure. Aside the present wave of the diaspora that is constituted by the so-called voluntary migrants, there is this element of force in the making of the phenomenon that is the diaspora.¹ That is notwithstanding the Diaspora constitute themselves as influential segment in their new locations and have become a very vibrant force in contemporary international politics. This is because apart from the Jewish diaspora in the United States and, all over Europe, there is the Chinese diaspora, the Indian diaspora, the Latinos diaspora and the African diaspora, among others. The consequence is that, majority of them are domiciled in the

developed countries and have acquired skills that could be mutually beneficial both for Africans of the soil and oversea.²

The dispersal of the African peoples in significant numbers around the world took place during the slave trade era between the 15th and 19th centuries although before then Africans are known to be living in Southern Europe, the Middle East and Asia.³ But they were not in great numbers. Even then, records are abound that in these new homes, Africans distinguished themselves as servants, dock officials, courtiers, agriculturists, scholars and soldiers.⁴ It is worthy of note that, before the famous discovery of the Americas in 1492, Africans were seen living in Mexico and Central America. This is to say that even before the birth of Christ (BC), Africans had dwelled in many parts of America.⁵ Despite the presence of black Africans in America before the 15th century, and it was however during the slave trade that the world saw the largest involuntary migrations of blacks in world history.

The forcible migrations of Africans to the Americas was linked to the rise of capitalism in Europe and the Atlantic trade in slaves which was tied to an economic chain of demand and supply to the existence of large-scale plantation agriculture in America, which needed abundant human labor. Africans were definitely not the first to provide labor for the plantations. Records are abound that European indentured persons was the source of labor at the onsets. Largely that they were lazy and not amenable coupled with considerable complications of legal protection in Europe, the plantation managers turned their attention to Amerindians who curiously were weak and allergic to diseases. Consequently, Europeans turned to Africa and the rest was history.⁶ This buttress the fact that Africans are immune to tropical diseases. They are hardworking. Above all, Africans unreserved loyalty to the plantation managers was the incendiary, massive scale were ferried to the New World and for the period the slave trade lasted, millions of them were taken across the Atlantic via Europe.

It is a fact that the United States is known to be a nation of immigrants, which constitutes a large number of blacks after Brazil in the Diaspora. The United States is, thus, practically a gigantic diaspora. However, in the United States, the Jewish Diaspora is a very powerful force to be reckoned with. This is such that there exists an American-Israel Public Affairs Committee (AIPAC) whose goal is to galvanize a coordinated public policy partnership between the US and Israel. They strive to utilize the AIPAC platform to express their support and unflinching commitment to the State of Israel amid the hostility and danger posed to its existence by its Arab neighbors.

Furthermore, it is because of the influence of AIPAC as a Jewish lobby that the successive generations of Americans are very deferential to it and indeed, pay close attention to its wishes and generally refrain from criticizing Israel even when its shortcoming is obvious and not in America's interest.⁷ What then is the relevance of the African Diaspora question in contemporary international relations? Is it well-grounded like the Jewish Diaspora in the United States and other countries? Or what significant role can the African Diaspora play in the life of African countries? This paper therefore hopes to quarry the vibrancy of the African Diaspora, expectations, challenges and prospects for Nigeria, Africa and Blacks in the Diaspora and others are deliberated here.

A Conceptual Analysis: The African Diaspora

The African Diaspora like the Jewish Diaspora from which the concept was borrowed, is a characterization of the chequered brutality and challengingly inspiring historical experiences of Blacks and Africans from antiquity.⁸ The African Diaspora embodies the defining attribute of a product of coercive relocation of black peoples around the globe. Unarguably, until the official abolition of slavery in its last vestige (the US) in 1865 with the 13th Amendment of that country's constitution, the development of African diaspora was characterized largely by force, the dispersion of a people, whether individually or collectively, has never ceased to be inherently associated with force majeure. Even the contemporary diaspora is basically composed of economic migrants that were forced to emigrate by the imperatives of survival syndrome for overt economic motive that is irresistibly compelling. Basically, the African diaspora are those Africans that were forcefully or who voluntarily dispersed to other parts of the world at different epochs of history, but who have maintained without losing their Africanness in physical, spiritual and psychological context. Professor Okon Uya however noted that the African diaspora has been able to “create vibrant living communities whose culture and social institutions were discernibly African, varying in scale and intensity depending on such factors as ... disposition and commitment of the white society, and the nature of contact with Africa. All communities represented enclaves of African cultures and institutions which have flourished with varying intensities....The commonalities in cultures, religion, cosmology and world view have remained a major resource for fueling African Diaspora sentiments.”⁹

Thus, the psychological component in the characterization of the diaspora is very important because, some are merely physically Africans, with a huge psychological disconnect from the African continent and peoples. However, Okon Uya has identified three categories of the African diaspora, borrowing his first category from Ali Mazrui's concept of “Diaspora of Enslavement” (which equals the classical African diaspora), while the second category is “the Diaspora of colonization”, that is, the diaspora of the post-abolition and colonial era, in which the victims were survivors in exile or their descendants, causalities of colonial and post-colonial disruptions, and the third category, which is the new diaspora, coincides with the modern African diaspora and are still connected to Africa in a new deal appropriately described as “Afro-Atlanticism.”¹⁰

Add to the above Diaspora categories, is a product of the challenge of rapid economic, social and political developments and the crisis of democratization in contemporary African history. Although statistics are difficult to come by, given the magnitude of the exodus, it is estimated that millions of Africans leave the continent every year either as political asylum or greener pastures outside the continent. The implication of such exodus, in most cases, play an extremely important role in bringing political pressure to bear on the very factors in their home countries that drove them out. The best examples of these were the roles of the Diasporas in the anti-apartheid and liberation struggles in Southern Africa and the democratization struggles in Kenya and Nigeria.¹¹

There is yet a fifth dimension of the Diaspora, a product of globalization which has witnessed, the ascendancy of Africans, be they of the “soil” or of the “blood”, to high position of leadership in their respective countries, especially the US. These persons of African descent have added their voices to the elevation of Africa and the African Diaspora related issues to the fore in these nations. Such prominent Africans like General Colin Powell and Condoleezza Rice as Secretaries of State as well as Vice President Kamala Harris, an Afro-Asian-American etc. in US simply plays out the significance of diaspora issues in international politics.

Thus, there are also some instances in which contemporary diaspora is consciously cultivated. When the state of China, for instance, opened its doors to the rest of the world after the Cultural Revolution, it adopted as a deliberate state policy the exporting of its citizens overseas; and this policy is reputedly subsisting today. It is, perhaps, to tackle unemployment and youth restiveness at the proportion known since the Tiananmen Square massacre in 1989. But China ultimately creates the incentives that woo back the highly skilled segments of the diaspora to be partaker of that country's growth and development.¹²

Probably from the Chinese and Jewish examples, Africans on the continent and those in the Diaspora have learnt important lessons in solidarity, organization and mobilization of the existing political processes to their advantage, exploiting the guilt complex of their former oppressors what Ali Mazrui calls "turning martyrdom into a political resource." One major concern has been the increasing globalization of the reparations crusade for African victims of the slave trade, colonialism and neocolonialism as well as other African development challenges. This is to suggest that it is absolutely difficult to neatly delineate and categorize all epochs of the African Diaspora that conformed to all different classifications aforementioned, as each of the period overlaps into the other.

The reason is that the African diaspora is enormous. It has, in fact, been argued that "one out of every five black men lives outside Africa".¹³ The slave trade is recognized as having been responsible for this enormity in scale because it played the most critical role in the dispersion of Africans to other parts of the world. In fact, Brazil is home to a large population of black people estimated to be more than half of that country's 190.73 million people, being the second largest concentration of black people after Nigeria.¹⁴ The existence of the African diaspora has given rise to the reality of two Africas, which is the Africa of the home and the Africa of the blood, the former being Africans on the African continent (some of who are not black or of the blood, like trans-Saharan Africans) while the latter category are those that have African blood, as descendants of people of African origin but who, owing to the slave trade, have been dispersed and cannot pointedly locate their ancestral roots on the continent.¹⁵

However, even though the African Diaspora is scattered over many regions of the globe, it is those in the West (particularly the US, Europe, and Canada) that are of any significant socio-economic and political consequence, and upon whom the continental Africans of the blood invest some expectations. The fact is that the Brazilian blacks, though numerically strong, are gravely marginalized and disempowered lot that only found footing in the recent history of that country. The implication of this is that the African diaspora in Brazil as elsewhere is of no political and economic consequence for Africans on the continent, the way that the African diaspora in the US or Europe are expected to be.

It is pertinent to distinguish here between the expectations from the African diaspora that resulted from the slave trade and those that engaged on the voluntary migration, that is, the modern-day African diaspora that have recognizable African ancestry and the citizenship of African countries. The slave trade induced African diaspora (the involuntary migrants) what is referred to as the classical African diaspora while those with recognizable ancestry and nationality of today's African states (the voluntary migrants) as modern African diaspora.¹⁶ This classification of Africa's diaspora in the US corresponds with what Ali Mazrui referred to as a distinction between

‘African-Americans’ (for the involuntary migrants) and ‘American-Africans’ (for the voluntary migrants). In fact, it is in the latter case that President Barrack Obama is referred to as an ‘Afro-Saxon President’.¹⁷

The aforementioned classifications notwithstanding, but consistent with the traditions of the Diasporas, the World Bank recognizes that the African diaspora, particularly the classical diaspora is expected to do allot for mother Africa. According to the World Bank “relevant information of socio-economic and cultural blocs of collaboration to strengthen Africa’s response to globalization; tapping their capacity to lobby Western governments...combating HIV/AIDS, Malaria; resolving conflicts.... These include tropical agriculture in the face of climate change in the case of the Caribbean nations and Africa; and business development by Brazil in the Southern African region and renewable energy systems-biofuel; and drawing lessons and assistance to leverage remittances”.¹⁸

Issues in the Expectations of the African Diaspora

Because the African-Americans are the most significant component of the classical and even the modern African diaspora, they bear much of black Africa’s expectations. However, while the era of racial discrimination and economic marginalization lasted, not much was expected from them, being extremely hopeless in the US as elsewhere. The reverse was the case, as the independent African states that were of immense assistance to the African diaspora in the US and other countries through enormous diplomatic pressure on the American “white” government to leverage racism and institute a more liberally inclusive socio-political and economic system.¹⁹ Similarly, the independent African states also provided considerable assistance to the American civil rights movement, especially with the foundation of Pan-Africanism, the platform that simultaneously coordinated those civil rights movements, Africa’s liberation from colonialism, African solidarity and so forth.

Symbiotically, African countries have expectations from the African diaspora in the US, that is, the African-American community. These are expectations that based on what Ali Mazrui described as the “considerable potential value” of the Diaspora for Africa. Its characterization in futuristic stance as a potential value is understandable because the value and consequent expectations could not be realizable until the African-American situations are being democratized. But to adequately comprehend what this considerable value is, it is however important to briefly historicize the Jewish Diaspora in the US as a guide. It is a common knowledge that Jewish Diaspora in the US has significantly affects relations in diverse ways, especially the huge economic and military resources in defense of Israel.²⁰

There is no doubt that given the way the US support for Israel sometimes goes beyond Washington’s strategic interests, has been largely propel by the Jewish lobby in the US. This is a loose collection of groups that seek to influence American public policy toward Israel. Thus, encouraging the US to back Israel more or less unconditionally.²¹ Consequently, US has nearly always protected this Jewish interest around the globe, but unfortunately at the detriment of others. Washington can declare a nuclear alert with respect to the Middle crisis as well as diplomatic row for mere emigration concerns that was withheld from the Russian Jews, but would not care a hoot in defense of the notorious apartheid against black South Africans.²²

Probably informed by the experience of the Jews and the Indians with respect to the contributions of the Silicon Valley Indian professional association of US, all of which have practically shown that the diaspora can be deployed to further foreign policy objectives, economic growth and development. In fact, the Jewish experience has concretely showed the fact that the diaspora are kin groups that readily come to the help of their former homes in periods of exigencies. For example, Armenia is a small landlocked country that is bordered by hostile Turkic neighbors, however, with meagre resources, Armenia's diaspora provided it with money and supplies that enabled it survive the Turkish blockade. Besides Russia, Armenia's major source of support was its large, wealthy and influential Diaspora in Western Europe and North America. This was also true of Croatia and the Croatian Diaspora.²³ In light of the aforementioned, the World Bank recognize that "[...] the Diaspora accumulate human and financial capital for economic and social development in their host communities. Like contemporary migrants, the wider Diaspora has been contributing to development of their home countries by sending remittances and managing businesses in their home countries. Many members of the Diaspora work in skill sectors that are of critical importance to their home countries. Many accumulate knowledge to establish and manage their own enterprises and are equally at home with the general situation and business culture of both their original and host countries".²⁴

Interestingly, therefore, this is the kind of influence that African countries expected and still expect from the African-Americans in defense of African interests. Arguably, not much has been achieved by the classical African diaspora in the US as elsewhere along this line. This is not to suggest that they do not enjoy the same historical circumstances nor possess the socio-economic and political influence that is comparable to the American Jews, but largely because of a complex; the psychological disconnect between Africa and those in the Diaspora. Although some African-American leaders like Malcolm X, Martin Luther King Jr. and others shared what Ali Mazrui called sensitivity and expanded empathy with Africa, such isolated cases of sensitivity and empathy did not make any difference in the larger cycle of a psychological disconnect.

The aforementioned pan-African consciousness among some African-Americans notwithstanding, the psychological disconnect remained a potent force to be reckoned with. It was so pervasive disconnect that James Baldwin called it "the African Conundrum." Thus, this thought, metaphorically conveys the "historical alienation" and the bitter immemorial grievance that the African blacks of the soil share with Africans of the blood in diaspora. As Chinua Achebe however noted, it is that debilitating indifference which so many African-Americans show towards Africa and the awkwardness which so many of us Africans and African-Americans suffer in each other's presence.²⁵ This manifestation of condescension and low opinion of Africans on the continent, as aptly demonstrated by the likes of James Baldwin and Keith Richburg, among others have considerable damaging effect on the psychology of some Afro-Americans. This is ostensibly part of the muted cynicism, the mutual alienation and the bitterness between Africa and African-Americans,²⁶ especially those whose ancestors luckily immigrated to other regions of the globe.

This mutual psychological distrust had definitely not been there from the outset, it was partly invented by authors in the business of revisionism, the turning of history upside down. However, the African diaspora concerns for Africa and the resultant movement for their return to Africa had miscellany of factors such as intellectual, philosophical, ideological, and organizational. African-American scholars like Drs. E. W. Blyden and W. E. B. DuBois developed concepts that were

peculiar to Africa such as the African Personality, Pan-Africanism, and Negritude that became the intellectual bridge between Africa and those in the Diaspora. So also was the populist Pan-Africanist, Marcus Garvey's Universal Negro Improvement Association were efforts geared toward fighting for the rights of blacks in the US and the struggles of the African peoples on the continent.

But even beyond this is the manifestation of miscegenated Africans developing a condescending attitude towards others had thereby send a negative signal seriously undermining the ideals of Pan-Africanism, the ideology for positive action by all Africans and for Africa, which further attested the viewpoint that Pan-Africanism lacked philosophic systemization.²⁷ The totality of it all is that, Pan-Africanism as "race-consciousness minus racism; a case for African unity, liberation...links the African struggle to the Third World. For through solidarity, it universalizes Africa. In the spirit of Pan-Africanism, all men and women of African descent, forWhat concerns one, concerns others. Each African person is his brother's keeper. Africans have one destiny because they are from one nation".²⁸

The groundswell of this lack of internal solidarity even amongst the African diaspora in the US and other places in recent times was made strikingly evident when Barack Obama, himself a miscegenated African vied for the American presidency. The bulk of the skeptics about his candidacy were "black intelligentsia", some of whom, "so wrapped up in racial history", provided the fodder for the newspaper headlines. Of interest such intra-racial tension cannot be imagined, not in public glare, within the Jewish Diaspora. This is to say that the tension has caused so much fractiousness that the African-Americans have remained unable to form a strong common front to concretely galvanize and cohesively protect their cause in that country, not to talk about providing functional diaspora services for African countries.

American Public Policy and the African Diaspora Disconnect

The aforementioned diaspora contradiction is not a genetic but, rather, a social problem or at best human cultivation. This is attributed to the displeasure characterized by the relationship existed between some African-Americans held against the African continent for complacency to their plight in the Americas through the slave trade. There was a conscious public policy that the American government dashed the development of positive links between African-Americans and Africa.²⁹ The reason for this public policy direction of America is not far-fetched, the fact that the classical African-American community in the US is an aberration in the conscience of the American society, being a product of a negative legacy, the legacy of the slave trade that sharply contradicted the America's professed ideals.

This contradiction had given rise to the phenomenon of a negative legacy, a feared legacy. Thus, King advocates that, the slavery legacy postulates the Americans of African descent, who suffered the incarceration and racial discrimination, would continue to agitate in the American system, thus, pointing to a deeply rooted and latent prejudice that could be ignited any moment for as long as race remained a salient part of the American society. It is, therefore, in the US interest to resist any initiative that would venture this potential disorder in America to an external entity (the African countries) that would pose a huge threat to America's national security.

Stated differently, it was not in the US national interest to deliberately or not to encourage African-Americans to develop vibrant linkages with Africans on the soil. This fear for an alliance between the Africans in the Diaspora and those on the continent could be used as a launch pad to change the subordinate position of Afro-Americans as well as Euro-Americans in that country. Such alliance would seriously undermine the essentials of European colonial holdings and provide the incendiary for liberating African territories from colonialism. The resultant emergent African states could be expected to offer sanctuary to descendants of the victims of the African slave trade. This could lead to a powerful tide of black emigration. If this happened, the US economy would have suffered grave consequences. The summary truth of this negative slave legacy that had dashed the development of any systematic relationship between Africans in the diaspora and Africans on the continent was; four fundamental fears. These fears Mae King writes include: the fear of rebellion, the fear of integration, the fear of emigration and the fear of revenge.³⁰ Today, the historical forces that propelled those circumstances have also changed as US has democratized the civil rights of Afro-Americans in that country to have a meaningful relationship between them. Yet, the lingering question still persist, has any meaningful relationship comparable to the Jewish Diaspora and Israel developed? Is there any improvement in the Afro-American and African countries?

Despite the fact that those things that had caused mutual suspicion between them are largely leveraged in contemporary times, nonetheless, remained fundamentally grave impediment to the cohesiveness and solidarity of blacks all over the world. This is because the linkages between black Americans and the West Indians as well as black Brazilians, has been very insignificant.³¹ While articulating those of the classical and modern diaspora Okon Uya writes there has been evidence of increased recognition of their common problems and the challenges facing mother Africa, but the relationship between them is neither institutionalized, completely cordial or free from tension.³² Nevertheless, Afro-Americans, have, despite the challenges, played some significant roles positively shaping some US policies towards Africa.

This is that African-American lobby groups like the Congressional Black Caucus and non-governmental organizations as the Constituency for Africa all lobby the US government to respond to Africa's developmental issues and opportunity, which has long manifested in advocacies like the African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA) and the fight against HIV/AIDS, and more recently, the Coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic. However and importantly, African-Americans' have made immense contribution by influencing their country's public policy for the benefit of the mother continent, as was the cases of Condoleezza Rice and General Colin Powel in influencing President George W. Bush that contributed to end the devastating humanitarian and political crisis in Liberia in 2003, when that country drifted into crisis³³, for example. This is a remarkable indication that not every Afro-American is a Keith Richburg who would rather chides at the continent's misfortune with conflicts. Today, African-Americans proved to have transcended the "African conundrum" to frontally advocate for mother Africa.

For Africa, however, the modern generation of diaspora is expected to do more to assist the continent's growth and development, and they actually do more, particularly in the grassroots level. It is because contemporary African diaspora is organically connected to Africa, with identifiable genealogical links and nationalities. This grassroots' orientation enables this class of the diaspora to successfully forge transnational networks between African countries and the

countries of residence. For instance, African Diaspora in the Netherlands promotes links and networks between people in the host country and Africa. This culminates in diverse ways that helps remove cultural barriers and cement durable social ties between the people of the Netherlands and those in Africa.³⁴

Besides, they also gets involved in some development challenges facing African countries, particularly the campaign for debt relief, trade concessions for African countries, lobbying for favorable policies, and the opening up of markets for African products in the advanced countries. Furthermore, they engaged in private businesses and financial remittances that put more money in the economy of its respective countries, much more than the official donors. It also involved in the establishment of Information and Communication (IT) sector in its home countries, as well as setting up community projects like water and electrification, medical services, micro credit schemes and education trust funds.³⁵

Nigeria and Blacks in the Diaspora

Nigeria has been the champion of the blacks' course in world affairs, and home to the largest black concentration on the face of the Earth. This also craves for Nigeria to extensively direct its foreign policy on them for their desire to look on to at least one country in Africa they could call a home. To that extent as scions of Africa, they need to be closer to their ancestral continent, especially a country like Nigeria should be interested in their problems as well as areas of excellence. On a wider spectrum, there are some notable blacks in the Americas, Europe, Asia and the rest of the world with special skills who could be of help to Nigeria's vision of technological advancement. The tendency for this is to identify and make use of their acquired skills and energies towards targeted goals, and quench the burning psychological quest.³⁶ As aforementioned, the second largest concentration of blacks in the diaspora after Brazil is the US. The blacks in that country is a potential force as far as contemporary American politics is concerned. As a result, they always vote as a bloc, yet no African country has taken the bull by the horn, to catalyze them for its diplomatic initiative. One major sphere of Nigeria's economic diplomacy to link up with the Africans in the Diaspora is tourism. This is because Nigeria has the biggest population of Blacks in the world is a tourism attraction which should be taken seriously.

Apparently, for every 1 in 5 black Africans is a Nigerian and every 1 in 7 blacks in the world is a Nigerian. This is the whole truth about Blacks. Surely, it is a platform for one eco-tourism region which would be of interest to Africans in the Diaspora and can make Nigeria a tourist's destination. This would indeed make Nigeria a center of attraction to the black race and the world at large. This is to say if Nigeria should host two thousand diaspora tourists yearly and each of them spend three thousand dollars, Nigeria would be richer by six billion dollars yearly through this medium, if this is properly organized with Africans and others outside the continent as the target of Nigerian tourism, the industry would definitely overtake petroleum and gas as the chief revenue earners for the country.³⁷

Although a panorama of Nigeria's skills development shows that there are many skilled potentials in information technology and that specialists abound in the country, but history is replete with examples that most developed countries are centers of cross fertilization of ideas. No country feels completely complacent in the quest for innovations. Even the most advanced countries that has first

class brains and facilities are always critical of innovation, still opened their doors to skillful hands from other countries. Nigerians and other nationals for example are found in many sensitive and strategic sectors of the US economy, military and many other advance countries, thus their dreams of international leadership is assured. This is in line with the lottery policy through which a number of skillful individuals from other countries are obliged visa to the US is a part of this vision to maintain her hitherto world center of excellence.

In addition, unless Nigeria vigorously pursue this global aspiration the African giant would relapse to coma and make its contender South Africa, which is strategically and frontally vying Nigeria's leadership position in Africa a destination of sort. For this reason, Nigeria should create a congenial atmosphere to calibrate policies to achieving this global aspiration. It is to this that scholars opines African intellectuals everywhere, whether in Africa or Diaspora should participate to add spices to her development agenda. This is why it is strongly contended that deliberate efforts at bringing on board Afro-Americans who are skilled in various skills be sought to catalyze mutually beneficial project for Africa and the Diaspora.³⁸

Component of the Linkage

It has been established however in many circles that blacks are instrumental to the foundation of the world economy, that is, the contemporary globalization driven by market forces; that have plunge Africa underdeveloped for ages. It is a common knowledge that there is no country in the black world that is developed. But there are other races like the whites who are proud of such countries like the UK, US, Canada, and even the Asians that were colonized as Africa have their Japan, India, China and others described as Asian Tigers. These are countries that have raise their status amongst races that have imputed psychological meanings to their races as a result of their contribution in the match to human civilization. All in all, Africa do not have anything to share in globalization. This clearly means there is no country in the African continent that is worth the trouble for the black race.

This corroborate the view that the two pillars of Africa Nigeria and South Africa are regrettably crawling in the dregs. Though South Africa may have galvanize economic development and at the verge of transiting to the first world but at the detriment of blacks, the consolidation of this advancement becomes suspicious. While the former's economy is driven by petro-gas which is a non-renewable energy and this makes the country to be vulnerable. Even in the United Nations despite the considerable number, Africa countries pitifully yell in anguish.³⁹ What is more? And this obviously beg for answers in the Diasporas' synergy and participation in African affairs and development agenda.

The point to emphasize here is that just as the black's contributed to the development of Europe and America in the past, today black skills and technological know-how should be made available for the development of Africa, especially Nigeria. Therefore, Nigeria ought to take the initiative and Africans in the Diaspora ought to seize the opportunities.⁴⁰ This partnership with African countries, especially Nigeria would afford a good number of them opportunities to write their names on the sands of history and be fulfilled.⁴¹ This is however not a clarion call for the back-to-Africa Movement which was propagated by black leaders like Marcus Garvey, Martin Delany, among others. The reason is that Nigeria or Africa cannot absorb the whole of Afro-world; rather, such a call is for selected Africans in the Diaspora with skills mostly in the areas of science and

technology to participate with their Nigerian brothers to pioneer “a technological revolution in Nigeria,” that would benefit both the oversea and the continental Africans.

Problems and Prospects for Nigeria, Africa and the Diaspora

It is crystal clear that despite the efforts in the African Diaspora initiatives they are yet to be institutionally and maximally harnessed in a systematic manner by Nigeria and Africa for national development. The blame for this clumsy movement is bordered on lack of a clearly defined operational terms before the aspiration of the Diaspora can be solidified. This means there are problems of mutual suspicion between the Africans in Diaspora and governments in the African continent, despite the African Union’s declaration of the Diaspora as Africa’s sixth region. Obviously, the major problem is the lack of an institutional framework for engaging the diaspora.⁴² For instance, Nigeria established one of such platform with the Nigerians in Diaspora Organization (NIDO) to mobilize Nigerians in diaspora for their participation in the development of the country. This interface also midwived a complementary department, the Nigerian National Volunteer Service (NNVS). The NNVS “was specifically mandated to facilitate the involvement of the diaspora in Nigeria’s development process, but unfortunately this attempt at institutionalization was marred with many problems that ranges from distortion, misperception and bureaucratic bottle-necks”.⁴³ The fact is that NIDO became a huge avenue of corruption for both Nigerian bureaucrats and the Diaspora.

Furthermore, it is apparent that the challenges are the result of lack of knowledge and experience to deal with organization of this caliber, that is, diaspora groupings. This is because most of the countries, especially sub-Saharan African countries, development institutions “yet to establish a productive working relationship” with the diaspora. The implication is that it portend a great danger to link the development efforts undertaken by the African organizations with the development programs promoted by the mainstream development agencies.⁴⁴ This is why the World Bank submit that there is always an atmosphere of tension and suspicion, not only between the diaspora, but also between some Diaspora and their home government.⁴⁵

This definitely affects the Diaspora partnership arising from the balkanization and mutual tension as they are organized, in most cases, into ethnicity, religious, and welfare associations among others.⁴⁶ Thus, the Nigerian diaspora, is particularly notorious for this ethnic characterization. Unlike other Africans, such as Ghanaians and Ethiopians for example, the fragmentation of Nigerians in Diaspora, especially ethnic divisions, is the consequence of the inability of Nigerians abroad to collectively defend Nigeria’s interest in their host country.⁴⁷ Thus, they lack the attribute of most skilled human capital, which is the much required ingredient that would jump-start their country’s economies and improve their living standards.

There is also “incidence of no-return” syndrome amongst the African diaspora and commitment of some of the Diaspora to get release by their host countries. Thus making it difficult for them to make their skills available for their country’s economic growth and development, especially those that possess skills, and are employed in strategic sectors in their countries of residence (e.g. nuclear and space facilities), which is very delicate to come by. Therefore, the tendency to consciously cultivate the incentives to woo back the highly skilled segments of the diaspora to be part of the developmental agenda is very much absent in Nigeria and Africa unlike China.⁴⁸ This is the crux

of the lack of consolidation of the African Diaspora synergy geared for the development of mother Africa.

The fact that African countries lack the consciousness to cultivate and utilize the diaspora, and the benefits associated in engaging the diaspora for development. Nigeria, for instance, recognized the importance and need to apply the diaspora only in the year 2000 by President Obasanjo. Today, President Buhari's government has consciously established the Nigerians in Diaspora Commission (NIDC) to give significance and consolidate on the Africans in the Diaspora that offers an opportunity for synergy to develop and to down-play the daunting scale of poverty.⁴⁹ When accomplished, this is sure to recalibrate fresh energies and determination to stimulate and propel new opportunities for growth and development in the various African countries, especially Nigeria.

Conclusion

The paper has x-rayed the role blacks in the Diaspora could play in the development of Nigeria, and by extension the African continent. This is because blacks are found in all regions of the globe. While the spirit of adventure took some of these people to the nooks and corners of the world long before the birth of Christ (B.C), it was the slave trade that lasted for more than four centuries that took millions of blacks to Europe and the Americas. After the abolition of the slave trade and emancipation of the blacks from slavery, they have been able to acquire skills that a country like Nigeria may need. Globalization greatly increased the number of Africans emigration through brain drain to Europe, America and Asia and they are making waves in all aspects of life. The paper however called for a symbiotic relationship between Nigeria and Africans in the Diaspora with skills should be identified and coopted in the development, especially in the areas of science and technology, which is, the spring board for economic growth and development.

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